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1 **An explanation of episodic tremor and slow slip constrained by**
2 **crack-seal veins and viscous shear in subduction mélange**

3

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19

20 **Key Points:**

21 • Crack-seal veins in subduction mélange record repeated low-angle thrust faulting
22 under tensile overpressure

23 • The minimum time interval between thrusting events is comparable to recurrence
24 intervals of slow earthquakes

25 • Crack-seal veins and viscous shear zones in subduction mélange may be geological
26 manifestations of episodic tremor and slow slip

27 **Abstract**

28 Episodic tremor and slow slip (ETS) occurs in the transition zone between the
29 locked seismogenic zone and the deeper, stably sliding zone. Actual mechanisms of ETS
30 are enigmatic, caused by lack of geological observations and limited spatial resolution of
31 geophysical information from the ETS source. We report that quartz-filled, crack-seal
32 shear and extension veins in subduction mélangé record repeated low-angle thrust-sense
33 frictional sliding and tensile fracturing at near-lithostatic fluid pressures. Crack-seal veins
34 were coeval with viscous shear zones that accommodated deformation by pressure
35 solution creep. The minimum time interval between thrusting events, determined from a
36 kinetic model of quartz precipitation in shear veins, was less than a few years. This short
37 recurrence time of low-angle brittle thrusting at near-lithostatic fluid overpressures
38 within viscous shear zones may be explained by frequent release of accumulated strain by
39 ETS.

40

41 **1. Introduction**

42 A spectrum of slow earthquake behaviors, including low-frequency tectonic tremors
43 (LFTs), low-frequency earthquakes (LFEs), very-low-frequency earthquakes (VLFs),
44 and slow slip events (SSEs), has been detected from seismologic and geodetic
45 observations [*Schwartz and Rokosky, 2007; Peng and Gomberg, 2010; Beroza and Ide,*
46 *2011; Saffer and Wallace, 2015; Obara and Kato, 2016*]. Tectonic tremor is defined as a
47 persistent low frequency seismic signal that lasts for days to weeks but is interpreted to

48 represent a swarm of LFEs that accommodate shear slip on low-angle thrusts [*Shelly et*
49 *al.*, 2007; *Ide et al.*, 2007]. Slow slip is a geodetically detected, transient creep event
50 where slip speed exceeds average plate motion but is too slow to generate detectable
51 seismic waves. On some faults, slow slip events appear to repeat near-periodically in the
52 same location, and in some places these events are spatiotemporally accompanied by
53 LFTs, referred to as episodic tremor and slow slip (ETS) [*Rogers and Dragert*, 2003;
54 *Obara et al.*, 2004].

55 In subduction zones, slow earthquake phenomena generally occur in transition zones
56 between interseismically locked and stably sliding fault segments [*Schwartz and*
57 *Rokosky*, 2007; *Peng and Gombert*, 2010]. ETS events are typically observed along the
58 plate boundary thrust near the mantle wedge corner in relatively warm subduction zones.
59 These events repeat at least every few years, and thus lead to episodic transfer of stress
60 from the ETS region to the locked seismogenic zone; this stress change may contribute
61 to trigger megathrust earthquakes [*Obara and Kato*, 2016]. Recent studies in the Nankai
62 subduction zone have revealed that LFTs, LFEs, and SSEs occur along the plate
63 boundary at depths of ~6–9 km and ~15 km [*Yamashita et al.*, 2015; *Araki et al.*, 2017;
64 *Nakano et al.*, 2018]. The components of ETS can therefore be generated along the plate
65 boundary at depths much shallower than the mantle wedge corner.

66 Despite the importance for understanding the dynamics of slow earthquakes and
67 their relation to megathrust earthquakes, the underlying deformation mechanisms
68 responsible for slow earthquake-generated deformation remain poorly understood. This
69 shortfall in physical understanding arises from insufficient geological information on

70 slow earthquakes, limited constraint on the temporal relationship between slow
71 earthquakes and ordinary megathrust earthquakes, and poor spatial constraints on the
72 source area of slow earthquakes and the spatiotemporal relation between tremor and
73 slow slip. Whereas geological evidence for high-speed slip, such as pseudotachylyte
74 (solidified frictional melt produced by seismic slip), has been reported from subduction
75 zones [Ujii *et al.*, 2007; Ujii and Kimura, 2014], low-speed deformation responsible
76 for slow earthquakes have been attributed to brittle failure of relatively strong lenses
77 coincident with viscous shear in surrounding matrix [Skarbek *et al.*, 2012; Fagereng *et*
78 *al.*, 2014; Hayman and Lavier, 2014; Behr *et al.*, 2018].

79 The exhumed Makimine mélange in the Late Cretaceous Shimanto accretionary
80 complex of eastern Kyushu, southwest Japan (Figure 1) records progressive plate
81 boundary deformation during subduction of young, warm oceanic crust to a shallow
82 (10–15 km) frictional-viscous transition where temperatures reached 300–350 °C
83 [Mackenzie *et al.*, 1987; Hara and Kimura, 2008; Palazzin *et al.*, 2016]. This mélange
84 is exhumed from a frictional-viscous transition zone, typical of where slow earthquakes
85 commonly occur. We examine the potential record of slow earthquakes by considering
86 four key geophysical observations from active subduction margins [Rogers and Dragert,
87 2003; Obara *et al.*, 2004; Schwartz and Rokosky, 2007; Peng and Gomberg, 2010;
88 Beroza and Ide, 2011; Saffer and Wallace, 2015; Obara and Kato, 2016; Wallace *et al.*,
89 2016; Araki *et al.*, 2017]: (1) slow earthquakes typically occur in regions of high fluid
90 pressure and low effective stress; (2) VLFs, and triggered swarms of LFs associated
91 with SSEs, have very low stress drops (tens of kilopascal) implying that the effective

92 fault strength is very weak and sensitive to perturbations; (3) when the focal mechanism
93 is determined, slow earthquakes commonly exhibit shear slip on low-angle thrust faults
94 subparallel to the plate boundary interface; and (4) ETS events repeat every several
95 months to a few years.

96

97 **2. Geological setting**

98 The Shimanto accretionary complex distributed along the Pacific side of southwest
99 Japan has been believed to represent an ancient on-land analog of the Nankai Trough
100 subduction zone (Figure 1a) [*Ujiie and Kimura, 2014*]. The Makimine mélange in the
101 Shimanto accretionary complex of eastern Kyushu is Cenomanian to
102 Campanian/Maastrichtian in age (Late Cretaceous) and experienced prehnite-actinolite
103 to greenschist facies metamorphism at 10–15 km depth [*Hara and Kimura, 2008*;
104 *Palazzin et al., 2016*]. The maximum temperatures determined from Raman spectra of
105 carbonaceous material, vitrinite reflectance, and illite crystallinity range from 300 to
106 350 °C [*Hara and Kimura, 2008*; *Palazzin et al., 2016*; supporting information]. The
107 mélange generally dips north-northwestward. The Makimine mélange preserves ocean
108 plate stratigraphy composed, in ascending order, of (1) mudstone-dominated mélange
109 containing basalt lenses and hemipelagic red mudstone at the base, (2) reddish brown
110 tuff, and (3) sandstone-mudstone mélange and coherent turbidites (Figure 1b). This
111 stratigraphy is repeated at least twice along the coastal exposure, possibly caused by
112 duplex underplating after subduction, with the apparent thickness of each thrust sheet in
113 the range 1300–1600 m. The subduction-related deformation at the frictional-viscous

114 transition is well preserved [*Mackenzie et al.*, 1987; *Palazzin et al.*, 2016]. Stretching
115 lineations defined by aligned mica prisms, quartz rods, and long axes of sandstone
116 blocks are particularly well developed in the structurally lower part of the *mélange*
117 (Figure 1c). This lineation represents constrictional strain and is interpreted as parallel
118 to the tectonic transport direction during subduction-related deformation, and indicates
119 that the subduction direction was perpendicular to the general strike of the *mélange*
120 (Figure 1d).

121

122 **3. Crack-seal veins and viscous shear zones in subduction *mélange***

123 A 10–60 m thick zone where quartz veins are highly concentrated occurs in the
124 lower part of the Makimine *mélange*, within which a penetrative foliation is defined by
125 pressure solution cleavage (Figure 1b). Along-strike continuity and across-strike
126 structural repetition of the vein concentration zone, and no spatial correlation between
127 the vein distribution zone and the thrust accommodating underplating, indicate that the
128 zone of vein concentration was formed during subduction and prior to the underplating
129 that incorporated the *mélange* into the overlying accretionary prism (Figure 1b). Shear
130 veins, foliation-parallel extension veins, subvertical extension veins, and viscous shear
131 zones are recognized within the vein concentration zone (Figure 2).

132 Shear veins are subparallel to the *mélange* foliation, with along-strike length ranging
133 from 1 to 10 m (typically about 1 m) (Figures 2a and 3a). Shear veins are laminated and
134 fibrous (Figure 2b), representing multiple episodes of dilation and quartz precipitation
135 along shear surfaces. The internal texture of shear veins is characterized by crack-seal

136 texture defined by phyllosilicate inclusion bands subparallel to vein margins, with
137 spacing ranging from 20 to 38 μm (Figure 2c and supporting information). At dilational
138 stepovers, the inclusion bands are oblique to vein margins, and slip increments
139 determined from fiber growth increments are 0.1–0.2 mm (Figure 2d). On the basis of
140 the dip direction of inclusion bands at dilational stepovers and steps on the vein surfaces,
141 shear veins exhibit thrust shear sense (Figures 2b and 2d). Slickenfiber orientations are
142 consistent with the top-SSE shear direction determined from the trend of stretching
143 lineations (Figures 1d and 3a). Tectonic reconstructions indicate subduction towards the
144 NNW [Whittaker *et al.*, 2007; Müller *et al.*, 2008], consistent with top-SSE shear, and
145 thus the kinematics of both stretching lineations and localized, frictional shear veins are
146 compatible with low-angle thrust faulting during subduction.

147 Foliation-parallel extension veins also show crack-seal texture marked by
148 development of inclusion bands of ~28–42 μm spacing but lack dilational stepovers and
149 slickenfibers on vein surfaces (Figure 2a). The length of foliation-parallel extension
150 veins along strike is typically ~1 m, similar to that of shear veins. Subvertical extension
151 veins are straight or sigmoidal, commonly constituting localized *en echelon* arrays
152 (Figure 2e). Quartz crystals within the subvertical veins are elongate with long axes
153 perpendicular to vein margins (Figure 2f), and a crack-seal texture is defined by 25 μm
154 spaced inclusion bands aligned parallel to vein boundaries. Viscous shear zones are
155 defined by < 10 m thick zones of rotated *mélange* foliations (Figure 2g). The viscous
156 deformation is accommodated by pressure solution creep, illustrated by dark selvages
157 and precipitates in pressure shadows, and commonly shows thrust shear sense. Some

158 shear veins, subhorizontal extension veins, and subvertical extension veins cut the
159 asymmetric fabric formed by viscous shear (Figure 2h), but are also themselves
160 viscously deformed (Figure 2g). These features indicate that brittle shear slip with
161 tensile fracturing and viscous shear occurred contemporaneously.

162

163 **4. Low-angle thrust faulting under tensile overpressure**

164 Pressure solution cleavage forms perpendicular to the greatest principal
165 compressive stress (σ_1) and thus the low-angle foliation implies a subvertical σ_1 ,
166 consistent with subvertical extension veins. However, this foliation reflects finite strain
167 and may therefore reflect long-term subvertical shortening, rather than stresses driving
168 fracturing [e.g. *Fisher and Byrne, 1987; Ujiie, 2002; Fagereng, 2013*]. It is conceivable
169 that σ_1 was consistently subvertical and foliation-parallel extension veins involved
170 opening of low cohesion, weak planes. However, this interpretation becomes
171 problematic, because (1) it requires σ_1 to become tensile, and (2) it is difficult to explain
172 the gentle dip of crack-seal bands within shear veins and foliation-parallel extension
173 veins. We therefore suggest that the stress repeatedly rotated, which resulted in
174 subvertical extension veins and foliation-parallel extension veins formed in different
175 stress fields. As pointed out by *Meneghini and Moore [2007]*, both explanations above
176 require cyclicity in effective normal stress.

177 A very small angle ($\sim 5.5^\circ$) between the average orientations of shear veins and
178 foliation-parallel extension veins indicates that shear veins were formed as hybrid
179 extensional-shear fractures under low differential stress of $4T_0 < \Delta\sigma < 5.66T_0$ [*Secor,*

180 1965], where T_0 is the rock tensile strength, and $\Delta\sigma$ is the differential stress (Figures 3a–
181 3c). This is consistent with that shear veins opened at a high angle to the vein margin
182 (Figure 2c). The geometrical relation between shear veins and foliation-parallel
183 extension veins may represent fault-fracture meshes developed in a compressional
184 regime [Sibson, 2017], where thrust faults lie at very low angles to σ_1 , and the least
185 principal compressive stress (σ_3) is approximately equal to the vertical stress (σ_V)
186 (Figure 3d). Under such a compressional regime, shear veins and hydraulic extension
187 veins are expected to develop at near-lithostatic and supralithostatic fluid overpressures,
188 respectively, as a result of opening directions of subhorizontal tensile veins being
189 subparallel to the subvertical σ_3 . Supposing $T_0 = 1$ MPa, a low estimate for typical
190 pelitic rocks [Lockner, 1995] to account for the deformed nature of mélangé mudstones,
191 shear strength (τ) at a very low angle to σ_1 (5.5°) is extremely low, $0.38 < \tau < 0.54$ MPa.
192 In this model, the mutually crosscutting relationship between the shear veins and local
193 arrays of subvertical tensile veins, as well as the presence of stylolites and folded
194 phyllosilicate inclusion bands in shear veins (Figure 2d), imply that the local stress field
195 could transiently swap between vertical σ_3 and vertical σ_1 , which is also indicative of
196 low differential stress. If, like Fagereng *et al.* [2011], we assume a low shear modulus
197 of 3 GPa for the mélangé rocks, the stress drop for 0.1–0.2 mm slip increments on 1–10
198 m long faults is 30–600 kPa, consistent with very low driving stresses.

199 The observations and model presented here differ in geometry from that
200 described by Fagereng *et al.* [2011]. The vein system they describe, in the Chrystalls
201 Beach Complex, New Zealand, consistently shows coeval shear and extension veins

202 formed under a subvertical σ_1 . The steep σ_1 determined in the Chrystalls Beach
203 Complex is typical of weak, underthrust sediments [e.g. *Fisher and Byrne*, 1987],
204 consistent also with thrust faults there developed along weak, low cohesion, clay-rich
205 cleavage [*Fagereng et al.*, 2010]. In the Makimine mélange, a horizontal σ_1 explains
206 many of the brittle structures, but episodically the stress field switched to vertical σ_1 .
207 This may be a dynamic effect, as also seen in focal mechanisms before and after the
208 2011 Tohoku-Oki earthquake [e.g., *Hasegawa et al.*, 2011; *Lin et al.*, 2013]. Why the
209 dominant stress field differs between Chrystalls Beach mélange and Makimine mélange
210 shear veins is unclear, but may relate to differences in the frictional strength of the fault
211 surfaces or the bulk rheology of the mélanges. In both cases, however, thrust sense
212 faulting occurred episodically at low differential stress and near-lithostatic fluid
213 pressure.

214

215 **5. Time interval between crack-seal events**

216 The crack-seal textures in shear and extension veins indicate that discontinuous
217 deformation occurred repeatedly and we interpret the repetition to correlate with
218 temporal fluid pressure variations. To investigate the time required between each
219 crack-seal event, a kinetic model for quartz precipitation [*Rimstidt and Barnes*, 1980],
220 driven by movement of fluid down a pressure gradient, was applied for quartz-filled
221 shear veins (supporting information). The model considers the width of inclusion bands
222 in shear veins (20–38 μm), the typical length of shear veins (1 m), fluid pressure
223 reduction at the start of each crack-seal event, and ambient temperature of 300–330 °C

224 (supporting information). Assuming that subhorizontal tensile fractures require at least
225 lithostatic fluid pressures, and that opening of these fractures creates at least temporarily
226 an interconnected fluid pathway, we consider a local fluid pressure change equal to
227 lithostatic minus hydrostatic pressure at the time of fracture opening. At 10–15 km
228 depth with average rock density of 2600 kg/m^3 , this is a fluid pressure drop of 157–235
229 MPa. This large fluid pressure drop is consistent with various vapor/liquid ratios in
230 two-phase fluid inclusions within shear veins (supporting information). Assuming
231 precipitation rate controls the time of healing (i.e. silica can be transported to the open
232 fracture at least as far as quartz precipitates), the veins can close in less than 1.6–4.5
233 years (Figure 4). Quartz crystals are blocky and do not show collapse structures, which
234 is consistent with precipitation in an open crack that did not collapse. This lack of
235 collapse structures may be surprising upon a large fluid pressure drop, but could
236 possibly be explained by relatively fast precipitation from fluids moving through the
237 fracture system in response to increased fracture permeability [cf. *Vrolijk, 1987*]. On the
238 other hand, we note that the large fluid pressure drop may have limited crack
239 propagation and locally arrested shear displacement. We thus assume this $\leq 1.6\text{--}4.5$
240 years estimate corresponds to minimum healing time between deformation events. If the
241 fluid temperature is higher than ambient temperature, the model suggests that healing
242 time becomes shorter, and similarly, if precipitation is coupled to collapse of pore space
243 under increasing effective normal stress, healing rates will also increase [*Rimstidt and*
244 *Barnes, 1980*].

245

246 6. Discussion and Conclusion

247 Our results show that shear veins in subduction mélange record low-angle thrust
248 faulting at very small shear strength and near-lithostatic fluid overpressures, consistent
249 with plate boundary shear kinematics and key geophysical observations of slow
250 earthquakes in subduction zones. The time required between discrete vein opening
251 events, assuming complete healing of cracks defined by inclusion band spacing, gives a
252 constraint of $\leq 1.6\text{--}4.5$ years for the minimum time interval of repeated thrust faulting
253 events. This repeat time is comparable to recurrence intervals of slow earthquakes. A
254 large number ($\sim 100\text{--}150$) of inclusion bands in shear veins (supporting information)
255 indicate multiple occurrences of fracturing under elevated fluid pressure and subsequent
256 restoration of cohesive and tensile strength through hydrothermal precipitation. If the slip
257 increment of $\sim 0.1\text{--}0.2$ mm at dilational stepovers correspond to the shear displacement
258 during a single slow earthquake, $\sim 100\text{--}150$ inclusion bands suggest that cumulative
259 displacement along individual low-angle thrust faults is $\sim 0.01\text{--}0.03$ m. Alternatively, the
260 total displacement during a single slow earthquake event may be distributed into many
261 different shear surfaces. In this case, the slip increment of $\sim 0.1\text{--}0.2$ mm during one
262 crack-seal event could accommodate a small component of the total displacement during
263 that slow earthquake. Crack-seal shear and extension veins are also recognized in other
264 mélanges and metamorphic rocks exhumed from the source depths of slow earthquakes
265 [Fagereng *et al.*, 2011; Fisher and Brantley, 2014; Sibson, 2017]. Such crack-seal veins
266 may also record repeated slow earthquake events.

267 In the Makimine mélange, the intensely veined zone is tens of meters thick, and
268 involves a combination of viscous and frictional deformation. Such frictional-viscous
269 deformation zones that are narrower than the full width of a mélange shear zone have
270 been reported from other exhumed subduction zones, irrespective of deformation
271 mechanisms of pressure solution creep or dislocation creep [Rowe *et al.*, 2013; Fagereng
272 *et al.*, 2014]. Within a mélange shear zone, frictional-viscous deformation along narrow
273 zones could represent deformation at higher strain rates. The absence of geological
274 evidence of frictional heat (e.g. pseudotachylytes) in narrow shear zones suggests that
275 strain rate is slower than seismic slip rate. Therefore, if localization of viscous shear
276 into narrow zones implies higher strain rates [cf. Fagereng *et al.*, 2014], then these may
277 be candidates for slow earthquake zones. A common feature is coexistence of
278 mineralized veins and relatively intense viscous fabrics, implying locally elevated fluid
279 pressures and increased viscous strains, respectively. The geophysically observed
280 signature of such deformation may be transient slow slip faster than plate motion rates
281 (SSEs) accompanied by localized frictional failure (tremor containing LFEs).

282

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291

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398

399 **Figure 1.** The Makimine mélange in the Shimanto accretionary complex. (a)
400 Distribution of the Shimanto accretionary complex in southwest Japan. (b) Geological
401 map of the Makimine mélange along the east coast of Kyushu. The location of the map
402 is shown in Fig. 1a. (c) Stretching lineations developed on the surface of mélange
403 foliation. The pencil is parallel to NNW-SSE oriented stretching lineations. The brighter
404 bands represent intersection between foliation and kink bands. (d) Lower hemisphere
405 equal-area stereoplots showing orientation of stretching lineations in the mélange.

406

407 **Figure 2.** Representative deformation in subduction mélange. Half arrows indicate
408 sense of shear. FPEV, Foliation-parallel extension veins. (a) Macroscopic appearance of
409 a shear vein and FPEV along the strike. (b) Slickenfibers and step (black arrow)
410 developed on the surface of shear vein, showing thrust sense of shear. (c) Microscopic
411 appearance of a shear vein cut parallel to slickenfibers and perpendicular to the shear
412 surface under cross-polarized light, showing repeated episodes of cracking and sealing.
413 The near-parallelism between phyllosilicate inclusion bands (black arrow) and the vein
414 margin indicates that the shear vein open at a high angle to the vein margin,
415 representing a hybrid extensional-shear fracture. (d) Folded phyllosilicate inclusion
416 bands (black arrow) at dilational stepovers under plane-polarized light. The horizontal
417 dark lines represent stylolites. (e) Macroscopic appearance of subvertical extension
418 veins along the dip showing *en echelon* arrays. (f) Microscopic appearance of a
419 subvertical extension vein under cross-polarized light. (g) Macroscopic appearance of a
420 viscous shear zone along the dip showing thrust sense of shear. (h) Microscopic

421 appearance of a viscous shear zone under plane-polarized light, showing the
422 development of asymmetric pressure solution fabric cut by subhorizontal extension
423 veins.

424

425 **Figure 3.** Low-angle thrust faulting at a very low angle to σ_1 under tensile overpressure.

426 (a) Lower hemisphere equal-area stereoplots showing orientation of slickenfiber shear

427 veins, *mélange* foliation, and average orientations of slickenfiber shear veins and

428 *mélange* foliation in the vein concentration zone in the lower thrust sheet. (b) Schematic

429 of geometrical relation between shear veins and foliation-parallel extension veins in a

430 compressional regime with $\sigma_3 = \sigma_v$. (c) Mohr diagram showing conditions of a hybrid

431 extensional-shear fracture at a very low angle to σ_1 . τ , shear stress; σ_n' , effective normal

432 stress. (d) Schematic of fault-fracture meshes developed along the subduction plate

433 boundary.

434

435 **Figure 4.** Sealing time for the width (w) of inclusion bands in quart-filled shear veins.

436 (a) At depth of 10 km and temperature of 300 °C. (b) At depth of 15 km and

437 temperature of 330 °C.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

a

Figure 3.

b

c

d

Figure 4.

a $T=300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\rho=2600\text{ kg/m}^3$, $d=10\text{ km}$